

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES PRODUCED BY SPRAY DEPOSITION

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SYNOPSIS

The production of metal matrix composite (MMC) systems using the technique of spray deposition is described. Mechanical properties, including tensile and toughness of three MMC systems are presented: AA2618-SiC, AA7075-SiC and AA8090-SiC. These properties are compared with those of the respective unreinforced alloys and the effect of SiC on properties, ageing characteristics and fracture behaviour is discussed. The effect of increasing ingot size on mechanical properties is also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composite (MMC) systems based on aluminium alloys reinforced with particulate silicon carbide (SiC_p) have received considerable attention over the last few years. The potential advantages are well documented^{1,2}.

Aluminium alloy/SiC_p MMC systems have been produced by several methods based on mixing in either the molten (melt stirring) or solid (powder mixing) state. Spray deposition is a hybrid method in which the reinforcement is mixed with molten metal during atomization. This ensures intimate mixing without the production of a reacted interfacial layer or incorporation of oxide films. The present study describes part of a project aimed at developing this technique for the production of composite systems. Specifically the paper will describe microstructures and mechanical properties of three MMC systems; AA2618-SiC_p, AA7075-SiC_p and AA8090-SiC_p.

FABRICATION OF MMC MATERIALS

The spray deposition process has been described elsewhere^{3,4,5}. Currently ingots of up to 100 kg are being produced (for evaluation) at the Banbury Laboratories of Alcan International. MMC ingots containing SiC_p have been fabricated by extrusion, rolling, forging and remelting. Of these product forms, emphasis has been placed on the first two for evaluating the characteristic properties of this type of MMC. Standard equipment and tooling has proved acceptable for the processing of these MMCs although minor modification of fabrication conditions compared with monolithic aluminium alloys has been necessary. The following data has been primarily obtained from laboratory scale 10 kg ingots consolidated by hot and cold rolling to 1 mm sheet or extruded using an extrusion ratio of 15:1. In all tensile tests the stress axis was aligned parallel to the longitudinal direction of the product. All of the composite materials contain SiC_p with an average size of 13 μm. Comparisons are made with similarly processed direct chill (DC) cast monolithic alloys.

RESULTS

Tensile Properties

Stress-strain curves for all three systems show a higher elastic modulus, earlier departure from true elastic behaviour and a higher initial work hardening rate in the MMCs compared with the unreinforced alloys. Fig. 1 shows the peak aged properties of AA2618 MMC sheet compared with the base alloy and in Fig. 2 similar comparisons are made for AA7075 MMC and AA8090 MMC extrudate.

In the AA2618 system there is an increase in strength of 25 %, whereas there is no increase in the AA7075 and AA8090 systems. Previous work^{3,6} has shown that over a range of alloys, lower strength matrices reinforced with SiC_p produce a more pronounced increase in strength compared with higher strength matrices. This effect partly arises because the stress borne by the reinforcement is a larger fraction of the matrix strength in lower strength matrices. The ductility of all three systems is reduced by the presence of SiC_p .

Fig. 3 shows the variation of tensile properties with time at a particular ageing temperature in the AA2618 MMC system. The comparison is between a composite with 15% SiC_p and a similarly processed monolithic material. Over the whole range of ageing the reinforced material shows superior elastic modulus and strength but decreased ductility. The increase in modulus associated with SiC_p has been studied analytically by Withers et al⁷ and the present results have been shown to fit this analytical treatment⁸. The ageing response of the AA2618 MMC is similar to that of the base alloy as is that of the AA7075 and AA8090 systems showing the important role of the matrix in controlling the mechanical properties of the composite. The most noticeable difference is an increase in elastic modulus with ageing time in the composite system.

The toughness of the MMC systems is less than that of the equivalent monolithic alloys. Typical values achieved on AA2618 MMC extrudate are 28.9 MPam^{1/2} in the under-aged condition and 24.9 MPam^{1/2} in the peak-aged condition (measured in the L-T orientation with compact tension specimens (CTS)). These are approximately 30% below those of the monolithic alloy equivalently aged.

Fracture Behaviour

Fig. 4 shows SEM micrographs taken from both sides of the fracture surface of a tensile specimen and an optical section through the fracture. The system in this case is AA2618- SiC_p but the salient features are the same in the AA8090 and AA7075 systems. It is clear that matching of SiC_p across the fracture surface is possible demonstrating that fracture has propagated through at least some of the SiC_p . Matrix failure has occurred through void linkage and there are also clearly voids associated with the SiC_p although there is no indication of widespread failure at the SiC_p /matrix interface. It is also clear from the section through the fracture surface that cracks have opened up in a number of SiC_p away from the fracture surface. The area fraction, however, of SiC_p on the fracture surface is not significantly higher than that which would be anticipated from a random plane taken through the bulk of the composite. This suggests that during growth the crack does not actively seek or avoid SiC_p . In regions of locally high concentrations of SiC_p there is a noticeable effect on the crack path; cracks are observed to avoid such regions, presumably due to the local stress distribution leading to a modification of the plastic zone ahead of the crack tip or a local decrease in the effective stress intensity at the crack tip.

Investigations of the fracture surface of the CTS toughness samples reveals similar features to the tensile fractures. Fracture is observed to propagate through the SiC_p and the matrix fails in a ductile manner. No interfacial failure has been observed within the range of stress or ageing conditions investigated. In the fatigue region of the toughness fractures, however, the fracture morphology is significantly different (Fig. 5). There is little sign of SiC_p on the fracture surface in these regions and the crack propagates almost exclusively through the matrix. This observation could be explained by the lower stress intensities associated with the initial stages of fatigue crack growth being insufficient to overcome the local stress fields associated with the SiC_p .

DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of this family of MMC systems can be broadly summarized as follows. SiC_p produces an increase in elastic modulus in all three systems, and dependent on the strength of the matrix either an increased or equivalent strength. These increases are gained at the expense of toughness and ductility.

Fig. 6 shows data obtained from AA2618 MMC extrudate produced from 100 kg ingot, extruded on a commercial press to thick section (46 mm diameter round bar), compared with data from 10 kg ingot extrudate. Overall the mechanical properties are improved in the larger ingot giving both higher strength and modulus with equivalent ductility. This improvement arises from the greater consistency of the microstructure in the larger cross-section material. In the smaller ingots some of the decreased ductility and toughness can be attributed to incomplete consolidation of the extrudate. Evidence of this can be found in the presence of pores or clumps of SiC_p on the fracture surface.

The ageing characteristics of the MMCs vary in a similar manner to the monolithic aluminium alloys: Increasing ageing time results in a decrease in ductility and toughness related to increasing strength. The ageing response is unaffected by the presence of the SiC_p in the three alloy systems investigated. This observation is interesting when compared with others made on AA6061 MMC and AA2014 MMC reported previously⁴ wherein the AA6061 MMC system showed an enhanced ageing response whereas the AA2014 MMC did not. This implies that the observation of an enhanced ageing response in an MMC is critically dependent on the matrix alloy and thus the precipitating phase as well as the presence of the reinforcement. The precise nature of the ageing response can also be influenced by thermomechanical treatment during the ageing cycle, where the effect of local stresses generated either by the difference in CTE or the effect of mechanical working may affect precipitation within the matrix.

The effect of ageing on modulus in AA2618 MMC is unexplained at present. Initial experiments⁹ indicate that the occurrence of this phenomenon may be related either, to strengthening of the interface occurring during the ageing treatment or, relaxation of internal stress generated during the solution heat treatment.

The ductility of the MMC systems investigated is somewhat lower than that of their base alloys, this is also shown up in the reduced fracture toughness. The fracture surfaces in both tensile and toughness tests indicate a fracture mechanism involving void formation in the region of the SiC_p possibly initiated by fracture of the particles. These voids grow and eventually coalesce to produce catastrophic failure of the matrix. It is unknown, however, whether these cracks are either inherent defects within the SiC_p , or produced during the manufacturing process, or due to local stress concentrations arising during deformation prior to fracture. A direct effect of SiC_p on the fracture path morphology appears to result from a balance between the stress intensity of the growing crack tip and the local stresses generated in the region of the particles themselves. This has the effect of deviating the crack when either the stress at the crack tip is low (eg. fatigue) or when the local concentration of SiC_p is high (eg. in the region of groups of SiC_p).

The studies of fracture behaviour indicate that the decreased ductility and toughness in composites does not result directly from interfacial decohesion as interfacial failure is not observed even in the over-aged condition. This differs from the observations of Lewandowski et al¹⁰ on a AA7075- SiC_p system produced by a powder metallurgy method and may reflect fundamental differences in the fracture characteristics of MMCs produced through the two routes. This is due to the difference in the mode of incorporation of SiC_p . In the case of powder MMCs this can result in the incorporation of oxide particles, whereas in molten metal route MMCs, reaction between SiC_p and aluminium can take place if the SiC_p is exposed to the molten metal for long periods¹¹. The absence of a significant reaction in the spray deposited material can be ascribed to the short contact time between SiC_p and aluminium which is less than a few seconds. TEM investigations of spray deposited materials¹² show that precipitation is negligible at the SiC_p /matrix interface in the as-produced composite in direct contrast to observations of the interface in powder route MMC¹³ and pressure infiltrated SiC fibre containing MMC¹⁴.

CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical properties of the three MMC systems produced by spray deposition show an increase in elastic modulus associated with the presence of SiC_p and dependent on the strength of the matrix either an increase or equivalent strength. These increases are gained at the expense of toughness and ductility. The major difference in mechanical properties from monolithic aluminium alloys is the increase in modulus in the MMC systems. Table 1 lists the specific modulus for conventional structural materials, aluminium-lithium based alloys and the three MMC systems investigated. The AA8090 MMC system has nearly a 50% higher specific stiffness than steel, titanium and aluminium alloys. This makes this system particularly attractive for applications where weight savings are of prime importance, for example aerospace¹⁵.

Material	Modulus (GPa)	Density (Mg/m ³)	Specific Modulus
7075	72	2.8	25.7
Steel	200	7.7	26.0
Ti-6Al-4V	106	4.4	24.1
AA8090	80	2.55	31.4
Aa2618	95	2.84	33.5
AA7075	92	2.9	31.7
AA8090	100	2.62	38.2

Table 1 - Specific Moduli for Various Structural Metals

Outside of the aerospace industry these materials will be used in applications in which the inherent properties of aluminium based systems present a natural advantage but where conventional alloys are not used due to their comparatively low stiffness.

The majority of the data presented in this paper was determined on material produced from small (10 kg) ingots on a laboratory scale. The properties of this material demonstrate the technical viability of spray deposition as a means of producing MMCs. It has also been shown that material produced from larger (100 kg) ingot and extruded on a commercial scale has superior properties. This demonstrates a fundamental advantage of spray deposition over alternative methods of producing composite systems; it is practical, and indeed beneficial to mechanical properties, to scale up the process.

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Figure 1 - Peak-Aged Tensile Properties of AA2618 MMC Sheet

Figure 2a - Peak-Aged Tensile Properties of AA7075 MMC Extrudate

Figure 2b - Peak-Aged Properties of AA8090 MMC Extrudate

Figure 3 - The effect of Ageing on the Tensile Properties of 2618 MMC Extrusion

Figure 4 - Matching SEM Micros of the Surface of a Tensile Specimen and an optical Section through the Fracture.

Figure 5 - SEM Micro Showing fatigue crack initiation morphology (2618 MMC)

Figure 6 - Effect of ingot site on tensile properties of AA2618 MMC